

Evaluation of germination, cold tolerance, and seedling vigor of boro rice germplasm

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Boro rice cultivation is a special system of rice cultivation in low-productive, waterlogged, low-lying deepwater land during November-May in eastern India. In such land, neither kharif (Jul-Oct) rice nor rabi (Nov-Apr) wheat is successful because of excess water. The boro crop is usually sown in November and transplanted when the temperature starts rising from January onward. The average minimum temperature during this period varies from 8 to 12 °C. Crop productivity is very high (Thakur and Mishra 1990); consequently, boro rice has become popular in Bihar and eastern Uttar Pradesh. The suitability of rice varieties for boro cultivation mainly depends on their germination, tolerance for low temperature at the seedling stage, and seedling vigor.

Twenty-one rice genotypes received from different institutions—IRRI, Philippines; Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad; Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal; and RAU—were evaluated in this study. The plant materials were sown on 10 Nov and germination vigor scores were recorded using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (IRRI 1996).

Most of the genotypes developed at IRRI and RAU were superior to those developed at Chinsurah and Hyderabad, recording more than 80% germination (see table). The seedlings of these genotypes remained green. Genotypes IR53970-100-3-3-2,

Germination, cold tolerance, and seedling vigor of selected genotypes.

Genotype	Germination percentage	Cold tolerance score ^a	Seedling vigor score ^a
RAU1344-3-2	83.0	5	5
RAU1345-2	93.6	3	1
IR59471-2B-20-2-1	65.3	5	5
IR55275-8-8-1-1-3	86.0	3	3
IR56383-77-1-1-1-1	84.0	3	3
IR53970-100-3-3-2	83.6	5	5
CN869-5-14-1-1	79.3	7	7
CN815-KGR—882-5-2	65.0	7	7
RAU1411-4	64.6	7	7
RAU1411-10	56.0	9	9
PSRM-1-16-48-1	74.3	7	7
RP2194-14-2-6-1	75.3	7	7
RP2333-383-30	68.3	9	9
RP2240-86-84	64.0	9	9
RP2240-59-54	73.0	7	7
RAU1345-1-2	84.0	7	5
IR61608-2B-70-2-2-1-2	83.0	3	3
RAU1400-3-7-2B-1	81.0	7	5
Boro-5-1B-6-3-3-4-1-1-1	81.0	5	5
Prabhat (check)	89.6	3	3
Gautam (check)	84.0	3	3

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* on a scale of 1–9 for seedlings, where 1 = seedlings dark green, 3 = seedlings light green, 5 = seedlings yellow, 7 = seedlings brown, 9 = seedlings dead. From tillering to maturity, on a scale of 1–9, where 1 = plants have a normal color; rate growth and flowering normal, and 9 = plants severely stunted, with leaves brown, development much delayed, and panicles not exerted.

IR59471-2B-20-2-1, and Boro 5-1B-6-3-3-4-1-1-1 showed moderate tolerance for cold at the seedling stage. The highest seedling vigor was observed in RAU1345-2, followed by IR55275-8-8-1-1-3, IR56383-77-1-1-1-1, IR61608-2B-70-2-2-1-2, Prabhat, and Gautam. Temperatures below 10 °C have an adverse influence on water absorption by decreasing respiration, which ultimately slows down germination (Aleshin and Aprod 1960). RAU1345-2, IR56383-77-1-1-1-1, IR55275-8-8-1-1-3, IR61608-2B-70-2-2-1-2, Prabhat, and Gautam had similar cold tolerance scores and showed the least damage in seedlings.

They also had good seedling vigor.

An ideal genotype suitable for boro cultivation should have a high germination percentage, good cold tolerance, and high seedling vigor. The genotypes RAU1345-2, IR55275-8-8-1-1-3, and IR61608-2B-70-2-2-1-2 may be suitable for boro cultivation in the eastern region of India as they had a better score than Gautam, which was developed earlier (Thakur et al 1994). These genotypes even showed better recovery after cold stress. Their yield potential and tolerance for biotic and other abiotic stresses are being evaluated.

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A widely commercialized two-line super hybrid rice, Liangyoupeijiu

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A two-line hybrid, Liangyoupeijiu, was released by the Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences (JAAS) and the China National Hybrid Rice Research and Development Center (CNHRDC) from the cross Peiai 64S/9311 (no. 65002). The female parent, Peiai 64S, was an environment-sensitive genic male sterile (EGMS) javanica line bred by CNHRDC with the wide compatibility gene *S5-n* from Padi, a variety from Indonesia, and the temperature-sensitive male sterility character from an EGMS line, Nongkeng 58S, a mutant from japonica cultivar Nongkeng 58. The male parent was an elite line developed from Yang Dao No. 6, an indica cultivar released by JAAS.

Liangyoupeijiu is an improved plant type with erect uppermost leaves. Compared with the widely grown indica check hybrid, Shanyou 63, it has a higher light transmission rate and a lower light extinction coefficient from middle to late growth stages. With a high level of heterosis and plant ideotype, the hybrid showed high yield potential, good grain quality, and strong resistance to bacterial leaf blight and blast. The hybrid has a maturity of 150 ± 24 d, 15–16

Table 1. Growth and yield characteristics of Liangyoupeijiu using data averaged from 19 testing plots in southern China in 1999 and 2000 multilocation trials.

Plant height (cm)	Maturity (d)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles ha ⁻¹ (no. × 10 ⁴)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Seed set (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)
112 ± 19	150 ± 24	8.4 ± 2.6	2.6 ± 0.5	166 ± 59	76.5 ± 18.8	26.2 ± 2.4

leaves on the main stems, and an average grain yield of 8.4 ± 2.6 t ha⁻¹ (data obtained from 19 testing sites of the multilocation trials in southern China in 1999 and 2000). During the 1999-2000 national test for super hybrid rice in Hunan and Jiangsu, Liangyoupeijiu was grown at 38 testing sites (at each site, the hybrid was grown in a test field of 6.7 ha). Its grain yield averaged 10.5 t ha⁻¹. A grain yield as high as 15.3 t ha⁻¹ was obtained in Binchuan County, Yunnan Province, in 1999. Table 1 shows the growth and yield characteristics of the hybrid. Liangyoupeijiu has good grain quality (most of its quality parameters met the high-quality standards set by the China Rice Research Institute) (Table 2). As a result of the two-line system of seed production, the hybrid has consistently achieved a seed yield of 2–3 t ha⁻¹ (seed of 98% purity) in the last 5 years.

For yield potential and grain quality, Liangyoupeijiu is well

Table 2. Evaluated grain quality characteristics of Liangyoupeijiu compared with the standard.

Characteristic	Liangyoupeijiu ^a	Standard ^b
Brown rice (%)	81.1 ± 2.7	>81
Milled rice (%)	73.6 ± 3.7	>72
Head rice (%)	55.5 ± 9.7	>59
Length (mm)	6.75 ± 0.39	>6.5
Length/width	3.0 ± 0.15	>3.0
Chalk rice (%)	27.7 ± 22.0	<10
Chalkiness (%)	3.94 ± 3.46	<5
Transparency	1.67 ± 1.02	<2
Alkali spreading value	5.67 ± 1.29	>4
Gel consistency (mm)	72.1 ± 8.0	>60
Amylose content (%)	20.3 ± 6.2	<22
Protein content (%)	9.78 ± 1.39	>8

^aTested by CRRI in 1998-2001 at seven different testing sites.
^bStandard values for high grain quality (class I) indica rice in China.

known as the prototype of the “super hybrid rice,” its discovery hugging the headlines in 2000. The hybrid has been registered as the first two-line hybrid. It had spread to more than 2.5×10^6 ha during 1999-2002 in southern China and in Southeast Asia, including Vietnam and the Philippines.